

Investigation of Micro- And Mesomixing in A Jet Loop Reactor

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a study on the meso- and micromixing behavior of the liquid phase in a laboratory-scale jet loop reactor (JLR). First, the mixing behavior was examined experimentally using the Villermaux–Dushman (VD) reaction system. Three process parameters were

systematically varied, namely the flow rate of the main jet, the flow rate of the acid solution feed, and the distance between the two feed points. A dye was added to the system as a tracer to visualize mesomixing behavior. In addition, an indicator was used in combination with a neutralization reaction to visualize the highly localized reaction zone. The results showed that all process parameters have a significant influence on the micro- and mesomixing in the reactor, thereby affecting the selectivities of the reaction system. Second, a modified engulfment model, which considers both micro- and mesomixing, was coupled with empirical equations describing the centerline velocity and the turbulent energy dissipation rate for turbulent free jets. The model reliably predicted the selectivities in the micromixing regime. In the mesomixing regime, although the model could predict the effect of the main jet flow rate and the distance between the two feed points on the selectivity, it failed to predict the influence of the acid feed flow rate. A highly non-uniform energy dissipation rate distribution was identified within the reactor. Local energy dissipation rates of up to $4 \times 10^4 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ were observed. The mixing times derived from the experiments ranged from $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}$ to $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}$. Overall, the results demonstrate that the JLR achieves excellent micromixing performance, highlighting its suitability for mixing-sensitive reaction systems.

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1. Introduction

Jet mixers are frequently employed in the process industry as an alternative to impeller mixers due to their enhanced rate of mixing at comparable power consumption [1, 2]. In jet mixers, a fast-moving stream of liquid (jet) is injected into a slow-moving or initially stationary liquid (bulk liquid) [3]. A special form of jet mixers are jet loop reactors (JLRs). An overview of common JLR designs can be found in [4–7]. Generally, a JLR consists of a nozzle, a draft tube, and a baffle plate, and is characterized by internal circulation flow caused by a strong liquid jet [8]. Since a JLR does not have a shaft for the agitator, the system is significantly easier to seal than stirred tanks, making it attractive for high-pressure applications [9]. Due to their excellent mixing performance, JLRs are particularly suitable for applications in mass-transfer-limited multiphase reaction systems [10]. Additionally, the strong internal backmixing improves selectivity in parallel reaction systems where side reactions are of higher order than the main reaction [9]. The efficient internal mixing also ensures that internal temperature gradients in the reactor are small [11]. This efficient internal mixing, which leads to the homogenization of concentration and temperature gradients throughout the entire reactor volume, is also referred to as macromixing [12]. In general, the macromixing behavior of the fluid in the reactor is of great importance for conversion and selectivities of most kinetically controlled reaction systems [13]. However, mixing also occurs on smaller scales beyond the macroscopic one. Mixing can be divided into three time and spatial scales: macro-, meso-, and micromixing [14, 15]. Mesomixing describes mixing at an intermediate scale near the feed point, where a plume of fresh feed is mixed with the surrounding bulk fluid, typically governed by large eddies and turbulent dispersion [15, 16]. Micromixing occurs at the smallest scale, where local turbulence strain rates and molecular diffusion enable reactions to take place [16–19]. When the reaction time is comparable to or shorter than the time required for mixing at the meso- and micro-scales, these small-scale mixing processes can influence the product distribution [20, 21], as it is the case for many industrially important reactions [13, 22, 23]. Such reactions are referred to as mixing-sensitive. For mixing-sensitive reactions, many process parameters that are irrelevant for kinetically controlled reactions can have a crucial impact on selectivity, including the position, diameter, and orientation of the feed pipe [15], feed rates [13], and local energy dissipation rates [24, 25]. A major priority in industrial reactors is to optimize the yield of desired products [26]. Consequently, the mixing behavior of the fluids in the given reactor must be well understood. Because of its simple design, well-defined flow pattern, good macromixing performance, and the ability to achieve local energy dissipation rates on the order of $1 \times 10^4 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ [13, 27, 28], JLRs represent a promising reactor type for mixing-sensitive reactions [29].

The principle of jet mixing is also widely applied in specialized mixers designed for mixing-sensitive reactions. The meso- and micromixing behavior of other jet mixers, such as impinging jet mixers [30–32], jet-stirred vessels [13], and tubular reactors with jet injections [33, 34], has

already been investigated. While the macromixing performance of JLRs has been studied extensively [1, 8–10, 35], their meso- and micromixing behavior has not been examined in detail so far. The aim of this study is to fill this gap by investigating and quantifying the meso- and micromixing behavior of a JLR to evaluate its suitability for mixing-sensitive reactions. Furthermore, JLRs are well-suited for systematic studies of mixing and testing mixing models. Due to the reactor design, the internal circulation flow is well-defined, allowing the influence of design and operational conditions—such as jet velocity on macromixing behavior—to be clearly understood. Thus, the impact of operation parameters (e.g., feed rates) and design parameters (such as the relative positions of feeds and nozzle diameters) on meso- and micromixing can be systematically investigated and compared to model predictions.

In this study, the meso- and micromixing behavior of a laboratory-scale JLR operating in single-phase flow was investigated. A combination of experimental and computational methods was applied to characterize the reactor's mixing behavior. First, the mesomixing behavior was visually examined by injecting a passive tracer (Brilliant Black). Next, the location and approximate size of the reaction zone were determined by adding a color indicator (phenolphthalein) to a neutralization reaction. To quantify the meso- and micromixing performance of the JLR, the product distribution of the well-known Villermaux-Dushman (VD) reaction system developed by Fournier et al. [36] was analyzed under various operating conditions. This reaction system has proved to be an effective tool for evaluating mixing efficiency in different reactors [37–44] due to its detailed kinetic model [45], cost-effectiveness, and simplicity in UV spectrophotometric analysis [46]. In addition, the engulfment model for mesomixing [47] was applied. To adapt this model to the JLR, it was coupled with empirical equations for turbulent free jets. The model was used for two purposes: First, to predict the influence of process parameters on the product distribution and second, to calculate theoretical mixing times based on the experimental results. Our study showed that JLRs are highly effective reactors for achieving good mixing and provided new insights into the complex interactions of operational and design parameters and their impact on mixing.

2. Theory

2.1. Villermaux-Dushman Reaction

The Villermaux-Dushman (VD) reaction system is a commonly employed chemical system for assessing small-scale mixing behavior [39, 48, 49]. It provides a means to explore the relationship between process parameters and the meso- and microscale mixing dynamics. This system comprises competitive parallel reactions: an instantaneous neutralization reaction (Reaction (I)), a fast iodide-iodate reaction (Reaction (II)), and an equilibrium iodine-iodide reaction (Reaction (III)).

The distribution of reaction products is highly sensitive to local mixing conditions [50]. Under ideal mixing, the neutralization reaction quickly consumes all available acid, thereby suppressing the occurrence of the subsequent reactions. In contrast, poor mixing leads to localized acid overconcentrations, allowing the second reaction to proceed [51]. The iodine produced in the second reaction reacts further in the third reaction to form triiodide, which can be detected via UV-vis spectroscopy. The concentration of triiodide ions serves as an indicator of mixing quality [46]. Details of the kinetic model of the VD reaction system can be found in Manzano Martínez et al. [45].

2.2. Jet Loop Reactor

In a jet loop reactor (JLR), fluid circulation is generated by a high-velocity jet rather than by mechanical agitation. JLRs can be operated in either batch or continuous mode [52]. As shown in Figure 2.1, the reactor consists of a cylindrical vessel equipped with a centrally positioned draft tube, a nozzle located at the top of the reactor, and a baffle plate. An external recycle pump continuously returns liquid from the reactor outlet to the nozzle, where it is accelerated and discharged as a liquid jet. The liquid jet enters the draft tube with high momentum and entrains the surrounding fluid. This entrainment mechanism induces a downward flow inside the draft tube and establishes a circulation loop within the reactor. Upon reaching the baffle plate,

the flow is redirected and rises through the annular region between the draft tube and the reactor wall. The fluid subsequently returns to the nozzle region, where it is re-entrained into the jet, thereby completing the internal circulation loop.

Figure 2.1.: Geometry of the JLR including its principal components and a schematic illustration of the internal hydrodynamics.

The jet supplied by the nozzle is characterized by intense turbulence and elevated local energy dissipation rates, making JLRs attractive for applications requiring rapid mixing on the meso- and microscale. While JLRs are commonly employed for gas–liquid and liquid–liquid multiphase processes, their hydrodynamic characteristics are equally advantageous for single-phase liquid reactions that are sensitive to mixing. In such systems, high local energy dissipation rates and high local velocities are desirable to ensure the rapid dilution of freshly introduced reactants and to minimize concentration inhomogeneities. This can be achieved by introducing an additional feed stream directly into the jet region.

2.3. Engulfment Model for Mesomixing

The mesomixing engulfment model proposed by Baldyga and Bourne [47] extends the well-established micromixing engulfment model of Bałdyga et al. [53]. While the original formulation is based on a two-environment framework [54], the extended model introduces a third environment to explicitly account for mesomixing phenomena. At its core, the model describes the mixing of fluid elements originating from a fresh feed stream with the surrounding bulk fluid across both the mesomixing and micromixing scales.

Mesomixing is assumed to be governed by the inertial-convective disintegration of large turbulent eddies, whereas micromixing is controlled by the engulfment of fluid by turbulent eddies at scales close to the Kolmogorov scale. By coupling the mixing model with reaction kinetics, the influence of mesomixing and micromixing on the product distribution of competitive and consecutive reaction systems can be quantified.

The mesomixing engulfment model adopts a Lagrangian description of the mixing process. To represent the behavior of an entire reactor, the Lagrangian model is solved repeatedly for a

sequence of discrete fluid elements. After the simulation of each fluid element, the composition of the bulk phase is updated to account for the exchange of mass between the fluid element and the reactor contents.

Since concentration gradients on the reactor scale are not explicitly resolved, information regarding the reactor operating mode enters the model solely through the bulk-phase update step. Depending on the application, this update can be formulated for semibatch, plug-flow (PFR), or continuously stirred tank reactor (CSTR) operation. In the present study, the semi-batch reactor formulation was employed.

The model is based on the assumption that the fresh feed is initially mixed with the surrounding bulk fluid on the mesomixing scale. Within this mesomixed volume, no reactions occur. Subsequently, micromixing takes place within this volume, allowing reactions to take place [55]. This concept is illustrated in Figure 2.2 for a semi-batch mixing process in a JLR. In the engulfment model, the continuous feed is discretized into small fluid elements. For each of these volumes, the Lagrangian engulfment model is applied. For further details, the reader is referred to Ashrafmansouri et al. [44] and Bałdyga et al. [47, 53].

Figure 2.2.: Concept of the engulfment model for mesomixing for a JLR operated in semi-batch operation mode. The reactor (a) is divided into three environments (b): a surrounding bulk phase, a growing mesomixed volume and a growing reaction zone.

The volume fraction of the mesomixed volume $X^{(3)}$ increases over time following the growth law given in Equation (2.1).

$$X^{(3)} = \frac{X_0^{(1)}}{X_0^{(1)} + (1 - X_0^{(1)}) \exp(-\alpha/\tau_S)} \quad (2.1)$$

Here, $X^{(3)}$ denotes the volume fraction of the mesomixed volume $V^{(3)}$ in the whole fluid volume (reactor and pipes) $V^{(0)}$ according to Equation (2.3). τ_S denotes the time scale for inertial convective disintegration of large eddies and α represents the Lagrangian lifetime of the fluid element. $X_0^{(1)}$ is the initial volume fraction of the fluid element according to Equation (2.2) at

$\alpha = 0$, where $V^{(1)}$ is the micromixed volume.

$$X^{(1)} = \frac{V^{(1)}}{V^{(0)}} \quad (2.2)$$

$$X^{(3)} = \frac{V^{(3)}}{V^{(0)}} \quad (2.3)$$

Micromixing occurs exclusively within the mesomixed volume and is regulated by self-engulfment [56]. The volume fraction $X^{(1)}$ of the micromixed region, corresponding to the reaction zone, grows according to Equation (2.4).

$$\frac{dX^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = EX^{(1)} \left(1 - \frac{X^{(1)}}{X^{(3)}} \right) \quad (2.4)$$

Here, E is the engulfment rate, which depends on the kinematic viscosity ν of the fluid and the local energy dissipation rate ε , and is calculated according to Equation (2.5).

$$E = 0.05776\sqrt{\varepsilon/\nu} \quad (2.5)$$

As reactions occur exclusively within the micromixed volume, the model formulates a mass balance for the concentration of each substance i in this zone. The concentration of substance i in the micromixed volume evolves according to Equation (2.6), where $c_i^{(2)}$ is the concentration of substance i in the surrounding bulk phase and R_i represents the reaction term.

$$\frac{dc_i^{(1)}}{d\alpha} = E \left(1 - \frac{X^{(1)}}{X^{(3)}} \right) \left(c_i^{(2)} - c_i^{(1)} \right) + R_i \quad (2.6)$$

Equation (2.6) is solved for all species until all reactions are complete ($\alpha = \alpha_{\text{end}}$). The initial concentrations $c_i^{(1)}$ at $\alpha = 0$ correspond to the inlet concentrations of substance i of the fresh feed. During the solution of Equation (2.6), the bulk concentrations are assumed to remain constant. After processing fluid element k , the bulk concentrations $c^{(2)}$ are updated according to Equation (2.7).

$$c_{i,k+1}^{(2)} = c_{i,k}^{(2)} \left(1 - X_k^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) \right) + c_{i,k}^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) X_k^{(1)}(\alpha_{k,\text{end}}) \quad (2.7)$$

2.4. Turbulent Free Jets

As evident from Equation (2.5) and Equation (2.6), the local energy dissipation rate, ε , is a key parameter of the engulfment model. In addition, the local bulk-fluid velocity is required to estimate the characteristic time scale associated with the inertial-convective disintegration of large eddies, τ_S (see Section 3.4.1). Consequently, the application of the engulfment model to a JLR requires estimates of both the local energy dissipation rate and the local velocity field. As illustrated in Figure 2.2 and described in Section 3.1, mixing in the present study was assumed to occur within the jet generated by the main nozzle of the JLR. Therefore, the local energy dissipation rate and bulk-fluid velocity were evaluated along the centerline of the jet and used as input parameters for the engulfment model.

While Mathpati et al. [1] have shown that jets in JLRs are not self-similar, other studies achieved satisfactory predictions of the meso- and micromixing behavior in jet reactors [27, 57] when using correlations for free jets. In this work, we followed the hypothesis of [27, 57] and there we assumed that the local centerline energy dissipation rate and bulk-fluid velocity can be sufficiently well described by the empirical correlations developed for free jets.

A free jet is a stream of liquid that emerges into a slow-moving or initially stationary liquid [3]. Its behavior depends on the properties of the liquid and the stationary medium, the initial velocity, and the nozzle geometry. Free jets can be divided into three regions [58]: 1) The core region, located near the nozzle and characterized by a nearly constant centerline velocity, 2) the transition region exhibiting velocity decline, turbulence development, and increasing entrainment of the ambient fluid, and 3) the fully developed region, which shows a self-similar velocity distribution. The velocity and energy dissipation distributions in the core and transition regions strongly depend on the specific setup. In the fully developed region, which begins after approximately 8 nozzle diameters d [57], these properties follow general trends that allow empirical modeling [59].

Figure 2.3.: Schematic of a turbulent free jet emerging from a nozzle, showing the distinct jet regions as well as the centerline properties along the axial direction (adapted from [27]).

Within the fully developed region, the decay of the centerline velocity u_c along the jet axis can be described by Equation (2.8) [27]. Here, $u_{c,0}$ is the outlet velocity of the nozzle and x is the distance from the nozzle. The constants used in this work are chosen similarly to [27], with $A_1 = 5.15$ [60] and $A_2 = -d$ [61].

$$u_c = \frac{A_1 u_{c,0} d}{x + A_2} \quad (2.8)$$

Additionally, the decay of the centerline energy dissipation rate ϵ_c can be described by Equation (2.9) [57]. The constants were chosen as $A_3 = 50$ and $A_4 = -2d$ according to [57].

$$\epsilon_c = \frac{A_3 u_{c,0}^3 d^3}{(x + A_4)^4} \quad (2.9)$$

3. Methods and Materials

3.1. Experimental Setup

Figure 3.1.: Sketch of the JLR and the experimental setup used in this study. The detailed view shows the three investigated feed positions.

Figure 3.1 shows a schematic of the experimental setup, including the JLR used for all investigations in this study. The JLR was made from transparent PMMA to allow visual access to the internal flow. It had a total height of 250 mm and an inner diameter of 80 mm. The reactor was equipped with a central draft tube and a top-mounted straight jet nozzle. The draft tube had an inner diameter of 40 mm and a height of 130 mm. The top-mounted jet nozzle had an inner diameter of 1.8 mm, which produced the main jet in the reactor and drove the circulation flow. The liquid exited the nozzle as a high-velocity jet directed downward into the draft tube, hitting the baffle plate and generating an upward return flow along the reactor wall. The reactor operated in a single-phase semi-batch mode within a closed hydraulic loop, where the reactor outlet was connected to the inlet nozzle via a gear pump (recycle pump, P3) in an external recirculation circuit. The reactor outlet could flow either into the external recirculation circuit or into a waste tank (B3). The total volume of the reactor was 1080 mL on its own and 1378 mL when including the external piping in the recirculation circuit. In all experiments, the reactor was initially filled with fluid 2 from the storage tank (B2) using a gear pump (P2) through the main nozzle. The reactor was vented through an opening at the top lid. Once filled, the fluid inside the reactor was circulated in the closed circuit by the recycle pump (P3). Additionally, another feed (fluid 1) was introduced into the reactor by an HPLC pump (P1) through a stainless-steel capillary

with an inner diameter of 0.25 mm. This feed entered the reactor perpendicular to the main jet, right in its center. The injection position of fluid 1 could be varied along the vertical axis of the jet. In this study, three parameters were varied: 1. The flow rate of the recycle pump (P3) from 25 L h^{-1} to 220 L h^{-1} (jet flow rate). 2. The feed rate of fluid 1 (P1) from 2.5 mL/min to 10 mL/min . 3. The vertical distance x of the capillary from the main nozzle at three positions: $x = 5 \text{ mm}$, $x = 20 \text{ mm}$, and $x = 35 \text{ mm}$ (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1.: Investigated positions of the capillary of fluid 1. Here, x denotes the vertical distance of the capillary from the main nozzle. The inlet diameter d^{in} is 1.8 mm.

x/mm	$x/d^{\text{in}}/-$	jet region
5	2.78	core region
20	11.1	fully developed region
35	19.4	fully developed region

A sketch of the reactor, including its dimensions, can be found in Supplementary Information S.1. Details of the components used in the experimental setup can be found in Supplementary Information S.2.

3.2. Experimental Procedure

3.2.1. Flow Visualization

First, flow visualization experiments were performed to qualitatively investigate the flow structure and mixing behavior inside the JLR. These tests aimed to visualize the mesomixing structures and the reaction zone. Two approaches were used for the flow visualization experiments: (1) tracer experiments with Brilliant Black dye to visualize the flow field, and (2) acid-base neutralization experiments employing phenolphthalein as a visual pH indicator to identify the reaction zone. In both approaches, the injection position of $x = 20 \text{ mm}$ for fluid 1 was used.

Tracer Experiments

A non-reactive tracer solution was prepared by dissolving Brilliant Black dye in deionized water at a concentration of 0.1 g L^{-1} . The experiments involved injecting a pulse of approximately 5 seconds of the Brilliant Black dye dissolved in deionized water (fluid 1) into the circulating deionized water (fluid 2). The dye injection was performed using an HPLC pump through the same capillary as used for reactive experiments. The experiments were conducted at different dye injection rates $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ and jet flow rates $\dot{V}^{(2)}$. The resulting dispersion of the colored tracer enabled direct observation of the mixing behavior and flow patterns within the reactor. Images and short video sequences were captured with a digital camera mounted in front of the reactor. The recorded material was evaluated qualitatively, mainly to visualize the mesomixing structures and to check the penetration depth of the feed through the capillary.

Neutralization Experiments

Due to the formation of triiodide in the third reaction (Reaction (III)) of the VD reaction system, the solution develops a yellow coloration that intensifies over time as a result of the semi-batch

operation. This coloration complicates the use of a visual pH indicator to localize the reaction zone. To overcome this limitation, neutralization experiments were conducted using a different reaction system than the VD reaction system. Instead, neutralization between aqueous sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and acetic acid (CH_3COOH), which remains colorless, was employed. Under the assumption that both the neutralization reaction of the VD reaction system (Reaction (I)) and the neutralization of sodium hydroxide with acetic acid can be considered as instantaneous, the observed reaction rate in both cases is limited by the meso- and micromixing processes. Under these mixing-limited conditions, the observed reaction rates of both systems are therefore expected to be identical and equal to the local mixing rate. Based on this assumption, the location and spatial extent of the reaction zone were visualized using the neutralization of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and acetic acid (CH_3COOH). This provided a reliable estimate of the size and position of the actual reaction zone in the VD reaction system.

For this, aqueous sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and acetic acid (CH_3COOH) solutions were prepared using deionized water. Both solutions were adjusted to a target concentration of 0.1 mol L^{-1} . A phenolphthalein indicator stock solution was prepared by dissolving 0.5 g of phenolphthalein powder in 50 mL of ethanol. A few drops of this indicator stock solution were added to the NaOH solution until a strong pink coloration was achieved. The aqueous pink solution of NaOH plus phenolphthalein (fluid 1) was injected into the circulating acetic acid solution (fluid 2) via the HPLC pump. Upon contact with the acidic bulk, the injected base solution rapidly turned colorless as neutralization proceeded. The transient pink coloration marked the instantaneous presence of the injected base and enabled direct visualization of the reaction zone around the injection point. Images and short video sequences were captured with a digital camera to observe the local reaction zone.

3.2.2. Mixing Experiments with VD Reaction System

Quantitative mixing experiments were conducted using the VD reaction system to evaluate the influence of process parameters on the meso- and micromixing performance. For the mixing experiments with the VD reaction system, two separate solutions were prepared: a buffer solution (fluid 2) containing sodium hydroxide (NaOH), boric acid (H_3BO_3), potassium iodate (KIO_3), and potassium iodide (KI), and a diluted perchloric acid (HClO_4) solution (fluid 1). The concentrations of the buffer and acid solutions are summarized in Table 3.2. All solutions were prepared with deionized water that was sparged with nitrogen to eliminate dissolved oxygen. This step was necessary because dissolved oxygen can oxidize iodide ions to iodine [38]. Additionally, a specific protocol [43, 62] was followed to inhibit iodine formation during the preparation process. Details of the solution preparation are available in Ashrafmansouri et al. [44]. Information regarding the suppliers and purities of the chemicals used is listed in Supplementary Information S.3. Considering the potential for oxidation and light sensitivity, the buffer and perchloric acid solutions were prepared immediately before the experiments and used on the same day to prevent degradation. Exposure to direct light was also avoided [38, 43, 62]. To systematically investigate the influence of hydrodynamic conditions on mixing efficiency, three parameters—main jet flow rate, acid injection rate, and the vertical acid injection position—were varied. In each experiment, after establishing a jet loop flow of buffer solution (fluid 2) through the reactor, the

acid solution (fluid 1) was injected using an HPLC pump. The injection time was adjusted to deliver a consistent acid volume of 50 mL for each acid flow rate. For example, at 10 mL/min, the acid injection time was 5 minutes, and at 2.5 mL/min, it was 20 minutes. After completing the injection, the HPLC pump was turned off, and the recycle pump continued to operate for another 1 minute. Subsequently, a sample was collected from the outlet of the JLR and immediately analyzed by UV-vis spectroscopy to measure the concentration of triiodide. The UV calibration curve is provided in Supplementary Information S.4 and details on sample preparation for UV calibration are available in [44]. The same procedure was used for all experiments at different jet and acid flow rates, as well as various acid injection positions. Each experiment was repeated at least three times, so each data point shown in the subsequent figures represents the average of these measurements.

Table 3.2.: Concentrations of buffer and acid solutions.

	compound	formula	concentration / mol L ⁻¹
buffer solution	sodium hydroxide	NaOH	0.0060
	boric acid	B(OH) ₃	0.0120
	potassium iodate	KIO ₃	0.0024
	potassium iodide	KI	0.0120
acid solution	perchloric acid	HClO ₄	0.1000

In industrial production processes, JLRs can be operated continuously, in batches, or in semi-batch mode [52]. In this work, the semi-batch operation was chosen to minimize chemical consumption during the experiments. Owing to their very short characteristic reaction times, the VD reactions are confined to a small reaction zone [13] near the inlet and are therefore governed by local mixing conditions – such as local velocities and energy dissipation rates – rather than by global concentration gradients. Consequently, the mixing characteristics obtained from semi-batch operation are considered representative of continuous operation for the purposes of meso- and micromixing analysis.

3.3. Data Processing and Calculations

3.3.1. Segregation Index

The segregation index was used as a quantitative measure of the mixing efficiency in the JLR. It is a dimensionless parameter that quantifies the extent to which an undesired side reaction occurs in a parallel reaction system. The segregation index for the VD reaction system is defined according to Equation (3.1), where S_{II} denotes the selectivity of reactant A toward the product P of the undesired side reaction (Reaction (II)) and S_{II}^{ST} represents the maximum selectivity toward the undesired side reaction under conditions of infinitely slow mixing [36]. In the present reaction system, A corresponds to H⁺ and P corresponds to I₂ (see Reaction (II)). Since the neutralization reaction (Reaction (I)) proceeds almost instantaneously, the selectivity toward the side reaction (Reaction (II)) approaches zero in the case of instantaneous mixing. The segregation index ranges from 0 to 1, where a value of 0 corresponds to the case of perfect mixing and a

value of 1 corresponds to the case of infinitely slow mixing.

$$X_S = \frac{S_{II}}{S_{II}^{ST}} \quad (3.1)$$

The selectivity in the case of infinitely slow mixing S_{II}^{ST} is calculated according to Equation (3.2), where $c_B^{(2)start}$ and $c_C^{(2)start}$ correspond to the initial concentrations of borate (B) and iodate (C) in the buffer solution. A derivation of this equation can be found in Ashrafmansouri et al. [44].

$$S_{II}^{ST} = \frac{6c_C^{(2)start}}{6c_C^{(2)start} + c_B^{(2)start}} \quad (3.2)$$

The observed selectivity S_{II} is determined according to Equation (3.3), where $c_A^{(1)start}$ is the initial concentration of H^+ in the acid solution and c_P^{end} and c_Q^{end} are the final concentrations of iodine (P) and triiodide (Q) from the samples taken from the reactor after the experiment. Here, $V^{(1)}$ and $V^{(2)}$ are the total volume of the acid feed during the experiment and the initially present volume of buffer solution in the reactor, respectively.

$$S_{II} = 2 \frac{(V^{(1)} + V^{(2)}) (c_P^{end} + c_Q^{end})}{V^{(1)} c_A^{(1)start}} \quad (3.3)$$

The final concentration of iodine (P) is calculated by solving Equation (3.4) for c_P^{end} [62]. Here, K_{eq} is the equilibrium constant of the iodine-iodide reaction (Reaction (III)), which is calculated according to [45].

$$\frac{5}{3}(V^{(1)} + V^{(2)})(c_P^{end})^2 + \left(\frac{8}{3}(V^{(1)} + V^{(2)})c_Q^{end} - V^{(2)}c_D^{(2)start} \right) c_P^{end} + \frac{(V^{(1)} + V^{(2)})c_Q^{end}}{K_{eq}} = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

3.3.2. Integral Energy Dissipation Rate

To quantify the energy that is available to drive the mixing inside of the JLR, the integral energy dissipation rate $\varepsilon^{(0)}$ is calculated, which is defined as in Equation (3.5). Here, P^{diss} is the rate of energy dissipation in the reactor and $m^{(0)}$ is the mass of the whole fluid volume in the reactor.

$$\varepsilon^{(0)} = \frac{P^{diss}}{m^{(0)}} \quad (3.5)$$

Due to the small feed rates of fluid 1 through the capillary, its influence on the dissipated power can reasonably be neglected. Thus, the dissipated power P^{diss} is equal to the difference between the flow of energy supplied by the main nozzle and the flow of energy leaving the reactor at the outlet. Additionally, it is assumed that the influence of the geodetic height difference and the pressure difference between the inlet and outlet can be neglected. Therefore, only the difference of the flow of kinetic energy \dot{E}_{kin} must be considered. Assuming an incompressible liquid, the ratio of the flow rates of kinetic energy is related to the ratio of the diameters d^{in} and d^{out} of the

inlet and outlet as in Equation (3.6).

$$\frac{\dot{E}_{\text{kin}}^{\text{out}}}{\dot{E}_{\text{kin}}^{\text{in}}} = \left(\frac{d^{\text{in}}}{d^{\text{out}}} \right)^4 \quad (3.6)$$

With a diameter of 1.8 mm for the main nozzle and a diameter of 7 mm for the outlet, the outgoing energy flow rate $\dot{E}_{\text{kin}}^{\text{out}}$ accounted for only about 0.44 % of the incoming energy flow rate $\dot{E}_{\text{kin}}^{\text{in}}$. This means that the kinetic energy from the jet is almost completely dissipated in the reactor. Consequently, the integral energy dissipation rate in the JLR can be calculated according to Equation (3.7), similar to the approach chosen in Maly et al. [63], where $u_{c,0}$ is the velocity of the jet leaving the main nozzle according to Equation (3.8).

$$\varepsilon^{(0)} = \frac{\dot{V}^{(2)} u_{c,0}^2}{2V^{(0)}} \quad (3.7)$$

$$u_{c,0} = \frac{4\dot{V}^{(2)}}{\pi(d^{\text{in}})^2} \quad (3.8)$$

3.4. Model Application

In this study, the engulfment model for mesomixing from Bałdyga et al. [47] was applied. To adapt this model to the JLR setup, the mesomixing time scale τ_S and the engulfment rate E had to be determined based on the operating parameters. In the JLR, the fluid motion is driven by the main jet emerging from the main nozzle. In all investigated cases, the capillary of the first feed (fluid 1) was positioned in the center of this jet (see Figure 3.1). In this work, the local velocities of the bulk fluid and the local energy dissipation rates were estimated based on Equations (2.8) and (2.9). By this, the local velocities and energy dissipation rates could be calculated as a function of the jet feed rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$, the diameter d^{in} of the main nozzle and the distance of the capillary from the main nozzle x .

3.4.1. Mesomixing Time Estimation

Depending on the ratio of the characteristic time scales, either turbulent dispersion or inertial convective disintegration can dominate the mesomixing step in the mixing process [47]. The choice of the mesomixing model depends on the limiting mesomixing mechanism [64]. To evaluate the suitability of the engulfment model for mesomixing developed by Bałdyga et al. [47] utilized in this work, the time scales for turbulent dispersion τ_D and the inertial convective disintegration of eddies τ_S were calculated for each experimental point according to the Equations (3.9) and (3.12). These time scales are influenced by the local velocities and energy dissipation rates. Those properties were estimated for different feed positions and jet flow rates based on the equations for free jets (Section 2.4).

The turbulent dispersion of a feed transverse to its local streamline is characterized by a time constant τ_D according to Equation (3.9). Here, $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ is the acid feed rate, u_c is the local velocity

of the bulk fluid and D_t is the turbulent diffusivity [65].

$$\tau_D = \frac{\dot{V}^{(1)}}{u_c D_t} \quad (3.9)$$

The turbulent diffusivity in Equation (3.9) was calculated based on the k - ε model from Launder et al. [66] as in Equation (3.10). Here, C_μ is a model constant set to 0.09 [67], and Sc_t is the turbulent Schmidt number, set to 1.0 following Pipino et al. [68]. k_t describes the turbulent kinetic energy and was calculated based on the turbulent intensity I_t and the local velocity u_c as shown in Equation (3.11) [69].

$$D_t = \frac{C_\mu k_t^2}{\varepsilon_c Sc_t} \quad (3.10)$$

Typically, for highly turbulent flow conditions, turbulence intensities lie within the range of 5 % to 20 % [70]. In the present study, a turbulence intensity of 10 % was assumed. The local velocity u_c was calculated based on the jet flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ and the distance to the main nozzle x according to Equations (2.8) and (3.8).

$$k_t = \frac{3}{2}(I_t u_c)^2 \quad (3.11)$$

The inertial convective disintegration of large eddies is characterized by a time constant τ_S according to Equation (3.12) [71]. Here, A_5 is a model constant, which is roughly 2 for fully turbulent flows [72]. Λ_C is the integral length scale of concentration fluctuations. Currently, there is no universal approach to estimate Λ_C [47].

$$\tau_S = A_5 \left(\frac{\Lambda_C^2}{\varepsilon_c} \right)^{1/3} \quad (3.12)$$

In this study, Λ_C was calculated according to Equation (3.13) assuming that the momentum of the secondary feed is negligible, following the approach from Baldyga et al. [47]. Here, u_c was calculated according to Equation (2.8).

$$\Lambda_C = \sqrt{\frac{\dot{V}^{(2)}}{u_c \pi}} \quad (3.13)$$

The mesomixing model is based on the assumption that inertial convective disintegration of large eddies is the limiting step. This condition is met if τ_S is greater than τ_D . Since the calculated values of both time scales represent only approximate estimates, a direct comparison in cases where the time scales are of similar magnitude was not considered reliable. Therefore, three distinct regimes were defined based on the ratio of the characteristic time scales. If τ_S exceeded τ_D by at least one order of magnitude (i.e., $\tau_S \geq 20 \tau_D$), the inertial convective disintegration scale was assumed to be the limiting mesomixing mechanism. If τ_D exceeded τ_S by at least one order of magnitude (i.e., $\tau_D \geq 20 \tau_S$), turbulent dispersion was assumed to be the limiting mesomixing mechanism. Intermediate ratios were classified as a transition regime, in which both mechanisms were assumed to contribute to the mesomixing behavior.

The calculation of the mesomixing time scales required estimates of the local energy dissipation rates and local bulk velocities. Only the acid injection positions of $x = 20$ mm and $x = 35$ mm were located within the fully developed region of the jet, which starts at approximately $x =$

14.4 mm ($8d^{\text{in}}$). In the approach applied in this study, local velocities and energy dissipation rates were estimated exclusively using correlations valid for the fully developed jet region. Therefore, mesomixing time scales could not be evaluated for the feed position of $x = 5$ mm.

3.4.2. Balance Equations

To apply the engulfment model for mesomixing to the VD reaction system, Equation (2.6) must be solved for all species involved in the reaction network (Reactions (I) to (III)). To calculate the reaction terms R_i in Equation (2.6), the kinetic model for the VD reaction system proposed by Manzano Martínez et al. [45] was utilized. The only difference is that, while in their kinetic model the iodine-iodide reaction (Reaction (III)) was modeled by an algebraic equation characterized by an equilibrium constant K_{eq} , here, the reaction was modeled as a set of two separate reactions following the approach from [73]. The resulting system of ordinary differential equations was simplified by applying the W-Z transformation proposed by Bałdyga et al. [74], which treats the first reaction as instantaneous. For a detailed description of the workflow and derivation of the equations, refer to Ashrafmansouri et al. [44].

3.4.3. Mixing Time Derivation

As with all selectivity-based measures, the segregation index depends on the specific reaction system employed. To enable a reaction-independent quantification of the mixing behavior, theoretical mixing times are derived from the experimentally measured segregation index with the engulfment model. This is done by substituting the engulfment rate E with the inverse of the mixing time t_{mix} according to Equation (3.14) [30]. Additionally, the mesomixing contribution in the model is neglected by setting $X^{(3)} = 1$ in Equations (2.4) and (2.6). The resulting model is quite similar to the incorporation model [45, 53, 75] while still inhibiting self engulfment. By this, a relationship between the product distribution and the mixing time is established.

$$E = \frac{1}{t_{\text{mix}}} \quad (3.14)$$

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Flow Visualization

4.1.1. Tracer Experiments

Figure 4.1 shows representative images from the recorded video sequences of the tracer experiments at a dye injection rate of 10 mL min^{-1} and jet flow rates of 25 L h^{-1} , 75 L h^{-1} , and 150 L h^{-1} . The images illustrate the dispersion of the injected dye stream within the jet-dominated flow structure in the reactor at increasing circulation flow rates. Videos and data files are available on Zenodo [76]. In all images, the injected tracer positioned at the center of the jet is clearly entrained into the downward-directed stream toward the draft tube. This observation confirms the presence of a stable flow field and a stable circulation flow in the reactor for all jet flow rates. Even at the lowest jet flow rate of 25 L h^{-1} , the highest dye injection rate of 10 mL min^{-1} caused no overshooting of the injected jet, bypassing of the main flow region, or wall impingement. This finding shows that the first feed (fluid 1) is rapidly incorporated into the bulk motion, confirming the assumption that the momentum of the first feed can be neglected (see Equation (3.13)).

The flow structures visualized by the tracer reveal characteristics similar to a free jet, as indicated by the lateral spreading of the tracer plume and the momentum-driven entrainment of the surrounding liquid. This suggests that the flow characteristics of the main jet within this region can reasonably be described as those of a free jet. It also shows that, within the examined parameter range, mesomixing structures can be observed, supporting the suitability of the hydrodynamic regime for the subsequent meso- and micromixing experiments. At lower jet flow rates, a pronounced and wide tracer plume is formed, which is transported by the flow into the draft tube. At higher jet flow rates, the dye feed is diluted more rapidly and the plume width decreases, which can be attributed to faster mixing with the surrounding flow. In addition, the size of the vortex structures within the jet visibly decreases with increasing jet flow rate, indicating a diminishing influence of mesomixing. This suggests that, at higher jet flow rates, a micromixing limitation can be expected.

4.1.2. Neutralization Experiments

Figure 4.2 shows the neutralization of the injected sodium hydroxide solution with the circulating acetic acid solution, as visualized by the color change of phenolphthalein. Only the results for the lowest jet flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ are shown, as no visible reaction zone could be observed at higher flow rates due to the lack of contrast caused by fast dilution. The pink coloration marks the

Figure 4.1.: Flow visualization using a tracer added at the feed position of $x = 20$ mm. The images show the tracer distribution at three different jet flow rates $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ (a) 25 L h^{-1} , (b) 75 L h^{-1} , and (c) 150 L h^{-1} and a dye injection rate $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ of 10 mL min^{-1} .

presence of unreacted base, while color disappearance indicates local neutralization due to mixing with the surrounding fluid. It appears directly at the capillary outlet and extends about 4 mm into the surrounding acidic bulk before fading completely. This corresponds to a negligibly small fraction of the reactor volume, highlighting the strong localization of the neutralization zone. The reaction is therefore very fast and highly localized around the injection point. These findings support the application of the engulfment model, as its assumption of locally confined reaction is satisfied. The observation that, at higher jet flow rates, the size of the reaction zone was too small to be captured indicates that the reaction is mixing-limited and strongly influenced by local hydrodynamics. Additionally, this suggests that the effects of local hydrodynamics on the reactions should be observable in the mixing experiments with the VD reaction system.

4.2. Mixing Experiments with VD Reaction System

Figure 4.3 shows the segregation index X_S of the VD reaction system as a function of the jet flow rate and acid flow rate at different acid injection positions ($x = 5$ mm, $x = 20$ mm, and $x = 35$ mm). For each acid injection position, a systematic decrease in X_S with increasing jet flow rate is observed. Such behavior shows that the system is sensitive to the local mixing conditions. It also indicates an enhanced rate of mixing at higher jet flow rates.

At a constant jet flow rate, higher acid injection rates yield larger X_S values, indicating the contribution of mesomixing in the mixing process. By increasing jet flow rates, the curves for different acid injection rates collapse onto a single curve, indicating a diminishing influence of mesomixing. For both the $x = 5$ mm and $x = 20$ mm positions, convergence occurs at approximately 75 L h^{-1} and 100 L h^{-1} , respectively. This clearly marks the onset of micromixing

Figure 4.2.: Reaction zone visualization with a neutralization reaction and phenolphthalein as an indicator injected at the feed position of $x = 20$ mm and at a jet flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ of 25 L h^{-1} and a dye injection rate $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ of 10 mL min^{-1} . The colored area indicates the local reaction zone.

limitations. The earlier convergence of the three curves corresponding to the different acid feed rates at the $x = 5$ mm position can be explained by the fact that, due to its closer proximity to the nozzle, local velocities are higher and therefore the integral length scale of concentration fluctuations is smaller. In contrast, for $x = 35$ mm position, the curves for different acid feed rates do not collapse onto a single curve; even at higher jet flow rates, substantial differences between the segregation indices for different acid injection rates persist. This observation implies that, at this feed position, the system does not fully transition into the micromixing-limited regime because the injected acid is not dispersed rapidly enough to overcome mesomixing limitations. The explanation lies in the fact that for free jets, both the velocity and the local turbulent energy dissipation rate decrease rapidly with increasing distance from the nozzle [35, 59]. These observations show that closer injection to the nozzle accelerates the transition to micromixing, while injection further downstream prolongs the mesomixing regime and may prevent full entry into the micromixing regime altogether.

As seen in Figure 4.3, changing the acid injection position from $x = 35$ mm to $x = 5$ mm reduces the segregation index values. It can also be observed that the influence of the acid injection rate is much smaller for the position of $x = 5$ mm than for the position of $x = 20$ mm. Additionally, although changing the feed position from $x = 20$ mm to $x = 5$ mm generally leads to a decrease in the segregation index, for lower jet flow rates, the feed position of $x = 20$ mm actually achieves lower segregation indices. Both observations can be explained by the fact that the feed position of ($x = 5$ mm) is located within the core region of the jet generated by the main nozzle. First, the centerline velocity within the core region is roughly equal to the inlet velocity and therefore higher than for other feed positions, which are located in the fully developed region of the jet starting at approximately 14.4 mm ($8d$). Because of the high velocity, the mesomixing contribution at $x = 5$ mm is smaller, resulting in a reduced offset of the curves at this acid injection position

Figure 4.3.: Segregation index X_S as a function of the jet flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ for different acid feed rates $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ and feed position. The colored background highlights the limiting mixing scale. Blue indicates a mesomixing limitation, while green indicates micromixing limitation. The lines are linear interpolations as guide to the eye.

compared to other positions. Additionally, the energy dissipation within the jet core is lower than in the fully developed region, as reported by Bałdyga et al. [27] and Deshpande et al. [35], which explains why smaller segregation indices can be achieved for the position of $x = 20$ mm than for the position of $x = 5$ mm.

These results demonstrate that all investigated parameters have a significant impact on the meso- and micromixing behavior of the JLR. This is consistent with theoretical expectations regarding the sensitivity of the VD reaction system to operating conditions [36, 37, 44].

4.3. Mesomixing Simulations

Figure 4.4 shows the resulting classification of the experimental points for the feed positions of $x = 20$ mm and $x = 35$ mm based on the corresponding operating conditions. For all investigated acid flow rates, the inertial convective disintegration mechanism is identified as the limiting mesomixing step at buffer flow rates between 25 L h^{-1} to 75 L h^{-1} . For $x = 35$ mm, the inertial convective regime extends to significantly higher buffer flow rates, remaining the limiting mechanism up to approximately 175 L h^{-1} . These operating conditions correspond to the cases in which mesomixing exerts a dominant influence on the overall mixing behavior, as discussed in the previous section. For $x = 20$ mm, the transition regime starts at buffer flow rates of approximately 100 L h^{-1} , while for $x = 35$ mm, this transition regime is only observed at the highest investigated buffer flow rate of 220 L h^{-1} . In both cases, the system is dominated by micromixing. Turbulent dispersion is identified as the limiting mesomixing mechanism only at buffer flow rates exceeding approximately 175 L h^{-1} for $x = 20$ mm. In this range, the system is clearly limited by micromixing. Overall, the results indicate that whenever mesomixing dominates the mixing behavior, the inertial convective disintegration scale is the limiting mesomixing mechanism. Turbulent dispersion becomes the dominant mesomixing mechanism only under conditions where the

Figure 4.4.: Limiting mesomixing mechanism for experiments at the feed positions of $x = 20$ mm and $x = 35$ mm. The colored background highlights the limiting mixing scale. Blue indicates a mesomixing limitation, while green indicates micromixing limitation. The lines are linear interpolations as guide to the eye.

overall mixing process is already limited by micromixing. Consequently, turbulent disintegration of eddies appears to be the relevant mesomixing mechanism for the present JLR setup. This finding provides support for the applicability of the engulfment model for mesomixing proposed by Baldyga et al. [47] to the system investigated in this study.

Figure 4.5 shows the comparison of the segregation index X_S predicted by the model and the experimentally measured values for the positions of $x = 20$ mm and $x = 35$ mm. For both feed positions, the model captures the monotonous decrease of X_S with increasing jet flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$. At jet flow rates of 175 L h^{-1} and higher, the absolute values of X_S are predicted with good agreement, particularly for $x = 20$ mm. In this range, the mixing behavior is limited by micromixing, meaning that the segregation index is exclusively influenced by the local energy dissipation rates. The good agreement of the model with the experimental results in this range indicates that the estimation of the local energy dissipation based on the centerline equation (Equation (2.9)) for free jets sufficiently describes the local energy dissipation in the jet emerging from the main nozzle in the JLR for the investigated feed positions.

For both positions, it can be observed that the offset between the lines for varying acid feed rates $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ increases with decreasing jet flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$. This demonstrates that the model can qualitatively predict the increasing influence of mesomixing at lower jet flow rates. While this qualitative behavior is captured, the model underestimates the absolute offset between the curves for different acid feed rates at low jet flow rates. This implies that the model cannot accurately describe the influence of mesomixing on the product distribution.

There are two possible causes for this discrepancy. First, the estimation of the integral scale of concentration fluctuations A_C is incorrect. Second, the mesomixing scale is not dominated by inertial convective disintegration, and therefore the model choice is invalid.

As previously mentioned, inertial convective disintegration of eddies is the limiting mesomixing step for the majority of the investigated experimental settings. Because the threshold for this

Figure 4.5.: Comparison of experimental data and model predictions for the segregation index X_S as a function of the jet flow rate $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ and the acid feed rate $\dot{V}^{(1)}$ for the $x = 20$ mm and $x = 35$ mm feed positions. The colored background highlights the limiting mixing scale. Blue indicates a mesomixing limitation, while green indicates micromixing limitation.

classification is chosen such that $\tau_S \geq 20 \tau_D$, the assumption is considered robust. Therefore, the model choice is still believed to be valid, and the inability to predict the influence of the acid feed rate likely arises from the first possibility: an incorrect estimation of Λ_C .

One obvious possibility is that the equation used to estimate the centerline velocity is not valid. However, to increase the spreading of the lines for different acid feed rates, the velocity would need to be lower. If that were the case, the mesomixing contribution would also increase the segregation index for higher jet flow rates, leading to higher X_S , which contradicts the good agreement between model and experiments at high jet flow rates.

Another possibility is that the reaction zone is not located within the center of the jet. However, the flow visualization studies (Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2) have shown that the reaction zone is small and located directly at the nozzle within the center of the main jet, thereby eliminating this possibility.

Currently, it seems likely that the correlation (Equation (3.13)) is not suitable to estimate the integral scale of concentration fluctuations in a JLR, even though the assumption of negligible momentum of the acid feed is met. Further research is required to clarify this matter. Future studies could consider employing computational fluid dynamics (CFD) modeling to calculate local dissipation rates and velocity fields, which may provide valuable insights into the underlying mechanisms driving concentration fluctuations in JLRs.

4.4. Mixing Times

Figure 4.6 presents the mixing times derived from the experiments as a function of the local energy dissipation rate. The required correlation to relate segregation index and mixing time

was obtained using the engulfment model and is provided in Supplementary Information S.5. The local energy dissipation rates were estimated using the centerline correlation given in Equation (2.9). The solid line represents the theoretical micromixing time according to Bałdyga et al. [53] for the case in which engulfment is the limiting micromixing mechanism. The symbols show the mixing times obtained in the present study for the JLR at the mid and low feed positions. For comparison, experimental data reported by Ashrafmansouri et al. [44] for a reaction mixing pump (RMP) using the VD reaction and the engulfment model for micromixing are also included.

Figure 4.6 shows that the mixing times derived for the JLR agree well with the theoretical micromixing time. At lower local energy dissipation rates, corresponding to lower jet flow rates, a larger scattering of the mixing times is observed for the three investigated acid feed rates. This scatter decreases with increasing local energy dissipation rate, which is consistent with the diminishing influence of mesomixing at higher jet flow rates.

For the $x = 20$ mm feed position, higher maximum local energy dissipation rates and correspondingly lower mixing times are observed, which is expected due to its position closer to the nozzle. For both the $x = 20$ mm and $x = 35$ mm positions, the slope of the mixing time trend decreases at higher local energy dissipation rates. This behavior is unexpected, since at higher jet flow rates the system approaches a micromixing limitation, for which the mixing times would be expected to converge toward the theoretical micromixing line. This deviation indicates that, at higher jet flow rates, the accuracy of the local energy dissipation rate estimation based on the free-jet centerline correlation decreases. This is reasonable, as the jet in the JLR is confined rather than free, and its characteristics are increasingly influenced by the loop flow at higher jet flow rates.

Figure 4.6.: Mixing time t_{mix} as a function of the local energy dissipation rate ε . Line: calculated micromixing time according to Bałdyga et al. [53]. Symbols: \triangle and \circ – experimental data from the JLR investigated in this study, \diamond – experimental data from the reaction mixing pump (RMP) investigated by Ashrafmansouri et al. [44].

The integral energy dissipation rates $\varepsilon^{(0)}$ calculated using Equation (3.7) ranged from $2.40 \times 10^{-2} \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ to $1.63 \times 10^1 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ for jet flow rates $\dot{V}^{(2)}$ of 25 L h^{-1} to 220 L h^{-1} , respectively. The corresponding local energy dissipation rates ranged from approximately $4 \times 10^1 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$

to $4 \times 10^4 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$. Thus, the local energy dissipation rates are approximately 1666 to 2453 times higher than the integral energy dissipation rate, indicating a highly inhomogeneous energy dissipation rate distribution. For reference, studies on stirred tank reactors reported ratios of local to integral energy dissipation rates of up to 118–138 [77, 78].

In comparison, the RMP achieved local energy dissipation rates of up to 10^3 W kg^{-1} and mixing times on the order of 10^{-3} s . Ashrafmansouri et al. [44] demonstrated that, for the RMP, the local energy dissipation rate can be reasonably approximated by the global energy dissipation rate for mixing-sensitive reactions. This shows that the JLR can achieve comparable or even lower mixing times than reactors specifically designed for mixing-sensitive applications.

The comparison of local-to-integral energy dissipation rate ratios between the JLR, RMP, and stirred tank reactors highlights that the energy dissipation rate distribution in the JLR is particularly inhomogeneous. From a practical perspective, this emphasizes that the choice of the feed position in JLRs is crucial to achieve high local energy dissipation rates and, consequently, short mixing times. The fact that selectivity depends on the choice of feed position poses a significant challenge for scale-up, as reliable methods for predicting relevant parameters—such as the local dissipation rate—are required. Table 4.1 further summarizes and compares the local energy dissipation rates and mixing times of the JLR with those of other reactor types.

Table 4.1.: Comparison of the local energy dissipation rates and mixing times for different reactors.

research group	reactor type	$\varepsilon / \text{W kg}^{-1}$	$t_{\text{mix}} / \text{s}$	model
Guichardon et al. [38]	stirred vessel	10^{-2} – 10^0	10^{-2} – 10^{-1}	incorporation model
Fang et al. [79]	Kenics mixer	10^{-2} – 10^0	10^{-3} – 10^{-1}	incorporation model
Manzano Martínez et al. [45]	rs-SDR	10^2 – 10^4	10^{-4} – 10^{-3}	engulfment model
Falk et al. [80]	micromixers	10^1 – 10^5	10^{-5} – 10^{-3}	IEM model
Ashrafmansouri et al. [44]	RMP	10^1 – 10^3	10^{-3} – 10^{-2}	engulfment model
this work	JLR	10^1 – 10^4	10^{-4} – 10^{-2}	engulfment model

5. Conclusion and Outlook

The aim of this study was to quantify the meso- and micromixing behavior of a JLR to evaluate its suitability for mixing-sensitive reactions. For this, the mixing behavior of a single-phase, laboratory-scale JLR was investigated using a combination of experimental and computational methods.

Mesomixing was first examined by injecting a passive tracer, which showed that the secondary feed is rapidly incorporated into the bulk flow and revealed characteristic mesomixing structures over the investigated operating range. The location and approximate size of the reaction zone were subsequently visualized using a color indicator in a neutralization reaction, confirming a strongly localized reaction zone typical of mixing-controlled systems. Overall, the tracer and neutralization experiments demonstrated that both mesomixing- and micromixing-dominated regimes can be investigated within the present experimental setup.

The meso- and micromixing performance of the JLR was quantified using the VD reaction system, evaluated over a wide range of operating conditions. The experimental results showed that the mixing behavior is strongly influenced by the process parameters. Increasing the jet flow rate led to improved mixing performance and correspondingly lower segregation indices. At lower jet flow rates, the acid feed rate had a pronounced effect on the segregation index, indicating a strong contribution of mesomixing.

Three acid feed positions at different distances from the main nozzle were investigated. Within the fully developed region of the jet, closer proximity to the nozzle resulted in lower segregation indices due to higher local energy dissipation rates. For the nearest feed position, the segregation index did not decrease further, as this position was located within the core region of the jet.

The comparison of characteristic mesomixing time scales showed that inertial convective disintegration of large eddies was the dominant mesomixing mechanism under conditions where mesomixing influenced the product distribution. This finding confirmed the applicability of the engulfment model for mesomixing to the investigated JLR configuration. The engulfment model for mesomixing was adapted to the JLR by incorporating centerline correlations for free jets to describe the local energy dissipation rate and flow velocity. The resulting model reliably predicted the influence of feed position and jet flow rate on the segregation index. This agreement confirms that estimating the local energy dissipation rate using correlations for free jets is sufficient for these parameters. However, the model failed to quantitatively capture the influence of the acid feed rate, i.e., the mesomixing contribution to the product distribution. This indicates that the approximation used for the integral length scale of concentration fluctuations is not suitable for JLRs.

The modeling approach further revealed that the JLR can achieve very high local energy dissipation rates and correspondingly short mixing times. At the same time, it highlighted a strongly inhomogeneous distribution of energy dissipation within the reactor.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the JLR can achieve local energy dissipation rates and mixing times comparable to those of specialized mixers for mixing-sensitive reactions, while retaining the operational flexibility and other advantages of JLRs. This renders JLRs an attractive and versatile alternative to commonly used reactor types for mixing-sensitive applications. The findings are particularly relevant for process engineers aiming to develop robust processes for reactions with strong mixing sensitivity.

For future work, the transferability of the results obtained under semi-batch operation to continuous JLR operation should be systematically validated. The influence of additional process parameters, such as alternative feed positions and multiple feed points, should be investigated. Of particular interest are multiphase applications, especially gas-liquid systems and strongly exothermic reactions. Furthermore, the inability of the engulfment model to accurately capture the mesomixing contribution highlights the need for an extended modeling approach tailored to the specific hydrodynamics of JLRs. Addressing these questions will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of meso- and micromixing processes in JLRs and thereby support their industrial application for mixing-sensitive reactions.

References

- [1] C. S. Mathpati, S. S. Deshpande, and J. B. Joshi, “Computational and experimental fluid dynamics of jet loop reactor,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 55, no. 10, pp. 2526–2544, 2009. DOI: 10.1002/aic.11853
- [2] H. J. Warnecke, “Macromixing characteristics of gas–liquid jet loop reactors,” *Acta Biotechnologica*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 111–121, 1989. DOI: 10.1002/abio.370090204
- [3] V. V. Ranade, “Towards better mixing protocols by designing spatially periodic flows: The case of a jet mixer,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 51, no. 11, pp. 2637–2642, 1996. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(96)00129-7
- [4] H. Blenke, K. Bohner, and W. Pfeiffer, “Hydrodynamische Berechnung von Schlaufenreaktoren für Einphasensysteme,” *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 43, no. 1-2, pp. 10–17, 1971. DOI: 10.1002/cite.330430103
- [5] P. Zehner, “Modellbildung für Mehrphasenströmungen in Reaktoren,” *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 60, no. 7, pp. 531–539, 1988. DOI: 10.1002/cite.330600706
- [6] P. Zehner and R. Benfer, “Modelling fluid dynamics in multiphase reactors,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 51, no. 10, pp. 1735–1744, 1996. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(96)00032-2
- [7] H. Warmeling, A. Behr, and A. J. Vorholt, “Jet loop reactors as a versatile reactor set up - Intensifying catalytic reactions: A review,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 149, pp. 229–248, 2016. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2016.04.032
- [8] F. Breit, O. Bey, and E. von Harbou, “Model-based investigation of the interaction of gas-consuming reactions and internal circulation flow within jet loop reactors,” *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 7, p. 1297, 2022. DOI: 10.3390/pr10071297
- [9] O. Bey and E. von Harbou, “Einfluss der Wechselwirkung von Reaktion und Fluidodynamik auf das Verhalten von Strahlschlaufenreaktoren,” *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 93, no. 1-2, pp. 191–200, 2021. DOI: 10.1002/cite.202000156
- [10] H. J. Warnecke, M. Geisendörfer, and D. C. Hempel, “Mass transfer behaviour of gas–liquid jet loop reactors,” *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 306–311, 1988. DOI: 10.1002/ceat.270110140
- [11] H. Blenke, K. Bohner, and S. Schuster, “Beitrag zur optimalen Gestaltung chemischer Reaktoren,” *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 289–294, 1965. DOI: 10.1002/cite.330370322
- [12] J. Baldyga and J. R. Bourne, “A fluid mechanical approach to turbulent mixing and chemical reaction part II: Micromixing in the light of turbulence theory,” *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 28, no. 4-6, pp. 243–258, 1984. DOI: 10.1080/00986448408940136

- [13] J. R. Bourne, "Mixing and the selectivity of chemical reactions," *Organic Process Research & Development*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 471–508, 2003. DOI: 10.1021/op020074q
- [14] D. Marchisio and A. A. Barresi, "CFD simulation of mixing and reaction: The relevance of the micro-mixing model," *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 58, no. 16, pp. 3579–3587, 2003. DOI: 10.1016/S0009-2509(03)00264-1
- [15] J. Bałdyga, J. R. Bourne, and Y. Yang, "Influence of feed pipe diameter on mesomixing in stirred tank reactors," *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 48, no. 19, pp. 3383–3390, 1993. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(93)80155-J
- [16] A. N. Manzano Martínez, R. Jansen, K. Walker, M. Assirelli, and J. van der Schaaf, "Experimental and modeling study on meso- and micromixing in the rotor–stator spinning disk reactor," *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 173, pp. 279–288, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.cherd.2021.07.012
- [17] I. S. Ertesvåg and B. F. Magnussen, "The eddy dissipation turbulence energy cascade model," *Combustion Science and Technology*, vol. 159, no. 1, pp. 213–235, 2000. DOI: 10.1080/00102200008935784
- [18] Z.-S. Mao and C. Yang, "Micro-mixing in chemical reactors: A perspective," *Chinese Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 381–390, 2017. DOI: 10.1016/j.cjche.2016.09.012
- [19] R. David and J. Villiermaux, "Interpretation of micromixing effects on fast consecutive-competing reactions in semi-batch stirred tanks by a simple interaction model," *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 54, no. 1-6, pp. 333–352, 1987. DOI: 10.1080/00986448708911913
- [20] J. Bałdyga and Ł. Makowski, "CFD modelling of mixing effects on the course of parallel chemical reactions carried out in a stirred tank," *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 225–231, 2004. DOI: 10.1002/ceat.200401992
- [21] R. A. Taylor, W. R. Penney, and H. X. Vo, "Scale-up methods for fast competitive chemical reactions in pipeline mixers," *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 44, no. 16, pp. 6095–6102, 2005. DOI: 10.1021/ie040237u
- [22] G. S. Reddy, N. S. Reddy, K. Manudhane, M. V. Rama Krishna, K. J. S. Ramachandra, and S. Gangula, "Application of continuous flow micromixing reactor technology for synthesis of benzimidazole drugs," *Organic Process Research & Development*, vol. 17, no. 10, pp. 1272–1276, 2013. DOI: 10.1021/op300325f
- [23] S. Huang et al., "Design and development of a new static mixing bioreactor for enzymatic bioprocess: Application in biodiesel production," *Renewable Energy*, vol. 197, pp. 922–931, 2022. DOI: 10.1016/j.renene.2022.08.003
- [24] J. Villiermaux, "The role of energy dissipation in contacting and mixing devices," *Chemical Engineering & Technology*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 276–287, 1988. DOI: 10.1002/ceat.270110137
- [25] M. Wiedemann, *Einfluss der lokalen Energiedissipationsdichte in Reaktoren auf Umsatz und Selektivität chemischer Reaktionen* (Berichte aus der Verfahrenstechnik). Aachen: Shaker, 2011.

- [26] K. Dahm, R. Hesketh, and M. J. Savelski, “Micromixing experiments in the introductory chemical reaction engineering course,” *Chemical Engineering Education*, vol. 39, pp. 94–99, 2005.
- [27] J. Bałdyga, J. R. Bourne, and B. Zimmermann, “Investigation of mixing in jet reactors using fast, competitive—consecutive reactions,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 49, no. 12, pp. 1937–1946, 1994. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(94)80078-2
- [28] J. Bałdyga, J. R. Bourne, B. Dubuis, A. W. Etchells, R. V. Gholap, and B. Zimmermann, “Jet reactor scale-up for mixing-controlled reactions,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 73, no. A5, pp. 497–502, 1995.
- [29] Z. Khan and J. B. Joshi, “Comparison of k–epsilon, RSM and LES models for the prediction of flow pattern in jet loop reactor,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 127, pp. 323–333, 2015. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2015.01.054
- [30] R. Gu, K. Cheng, and L. Wen, “Application of the engulfment model in assessing micromixing time of a micro-impinging stream reactor based on the determination of impinging zone with CFD,” *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 409, p. 128 248, 2021. DOI: 10.1016/j.cej.2020.128248
- [31] Y. Liu and R. O. Fox, “CFD predictions for chemical processing in a confined impinging-jets reactor,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 731–744, 2006. DOI: 10.1002/aic.10633
- [32] A. Nie, Z. Gao, L. Xue, Z. Cai, G. M. Evans, and A. Eaglesham, “Micromixing performance and the modeling of a confined impinging jet reactor/high speed disperser,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 184, pp. 14–24, 2018. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2018.03.032
- [33] L. J. Forney and N. Nafia, “Turbulent jet reactors,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 76, no. 6, pp. 728–736, 1998. DOI: 10.1205/026387698525432
- [34] L. J. Forney and N. Nafia, “Eddy contact model: CFD simulations of liquid reactions in nearly homogeneous turbulence,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 55, no. 24, pp. 6049–6058, 2000. DOI: 10.1016/S0009-2509(00)00209-8
- [35] S. S. Deshpande, M. J. Sathe, and J. B. Joshi, “Evaluation of local turbulent energy dissipation rate using PIV in jet loop reactor,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 48, no. 10, pp. 5046–5057, 2009. DOI: 10.1021/ie8007924
- [36] M.-C. Fournier, L. Falk, and J. Villiermaux, “A new parallel competing reaction system for assessing micromixing efficiency: Determination of micromixing time by a simple mixing model,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 51, no. 23, pp. 5187–5192, 1996. DOI: 10.1016/S0009-2509(96)00340-5
- [37] J.-M. Commenge and L. Falk, “Villiermaux–Dushman protocol for experimental characterization of micromixers,” *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, vol. 50, no. 10, pp. 979–990, 2011. DOI: 10.1016/j.cep.2011.06.006
- [38] P. Guichardon and L. Falk, “Characterisation of micromixing efficiency by the iodide–iodate reaction system part I: Experimental procedure,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 55, no. 19, pp. 4233–4243, 2000. DOI: 10.1016/S0009-2509(00)00068-3

- [39] S. R. L. Gobert, S. Kuhn, L. Braeken, and L. C. J. Thomassen, “Characterization of milli- and microflow reactors: Mixing efficiency and residence time distribution,” *Organic Process Research & Development*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 531–542, 2017. DOI: 10.1021/acs.oprd.6b00359
- [40] K. Cheng, C. Liu, T. Guo, and L. Wen, “CFD and experimental investigations on the micromixing performance of single countercurrent-flow microchannel reactor,” *Chinese Journal of Chemical Engineering*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 1079–1088, 2019. DOI: 10.1016/j.cjche.2018.11.026
- [41] W. Pei et al., “Influence of micromixing and shear on precipitation process in the jet-flow high shear reactors,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 300, p. 120640, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2024.120640
- [42] L. Chen, Q. Du, Y. Guo, X. Yang, and B. Chen, “Numerical modelling of effects of ultrasound-induced acoustic streaming on hydrodynamics in a confined impinging jet reactor using a non-linear model based on local velocity fluctuation,” *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, vol. 183, p. 109253, 2023. DOI: 10.1016/j.cep.2022.109253
- [43] A. N. Manzano Martínez, K. M. P. van Eeten, J. C. Schouten, and J. van der Schaaf, “Micromixing in a rotor-stator spinning disc reactor,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 56, no. 45, pp. 13454–13460, 2017. DOI: 10.1021/acs.iecr.7b01324
- [44] S.-S. Ashrafmansouri, A. Kraus, S. Osterroth, and E. von Harbou, “Investigation of micro- and mesomixing in a reaction mixing pump,” *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 525, p. 169785, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.cej.2025.169785
- [45] A. N. Manzano Martínez, A. S. Haase, M. Assirelli, and J. van der Schaaf, “Alternative kinetic model of the iodide–iodate reaction for its use in micromixing investigations,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 59, no. 49, pp. 21359–21370, 2020. DOI: 10.1021/acs.iecr.0c04901
- [46] J. M. Reckamp et al., “Mixing performance evaluation for commercially available micromixers using Villermaux–Dushman reaction scheme with the interaction by exchange with the mean model,” *Organic Process Research & Development*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 816–820, 2017. DOI: 10.1021/acs.oprd.6b00332
- [47] J. Bałdyga, J. R. Bourne, and S. J. Hearn, “Interaction between chemical reactions and mixing on various scales,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 52, no. 4, pp. 457–466, 1997. DOI: 10.1016/S0009-2509(96)00430-7
- [48] P. Guichardon, C. Baqueiro, and N. Ibaseta, “Villermaux–Dushman test of micromixing characterization revisited: Kinetic effects of acid choice and ionic strength,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 60, no. 50, pp. 18268–18282, 2021. DOI: 10.1021/acs.iecr.1c03208
- [49] T. Frey et al., “Local analysis of micro mixing for the Villermaux–Dushman protocol by using the imaging UV-Vis spectroscopy,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 205, pp. 822–829, 2024. DOI: 10.1016/j.cherd.2024.04.049

- [50] M. Jasińska, “Test reactions to study efficiency of mixing,” *Chemical and Process Engineering*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 171–208, 2015. DOI: 10.1515/cpe-2015-0013
- [51] J. R. Bourne, “Comments on the iodide/iodate method for characterising micromixing,” *Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 140, no. 1-3, pp. 638–641, 2008. DOI: 10.1016/j.cej.2008.01.031
- [52] M. Schlüter, H. J. Warnecke, and P. Zehner, “Reaktoren für Fluid-Fluid-Reaktionen: Schlaufenreaktoren,” in *Handbuch Chemische Reaktoren*, W. Reschetilowski, Ed., Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2020, pp. 771–801. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-662-56434-9_28
- [53] J. Bałdyga and J. R. Bourne, “Simplification of micromixing calculations: I. Derivation and application of new model,” *The Chemical Engineering Journal*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 83–92, 1989. DOI: 10.1016/0300-9467(89)85002-6
- [54] R. O. Fox, “On the relationship between Lagrangian micromixing models and computational fluid dynamics,” *Chemical Engineering and Processing: Process Intensification*, vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 521–535, 1998. DOI: 10.1016/S0255-2701(98)00059-2
- [55] J. Bałdyga and S. Rohani, “Micromixing described in terms of inertial-convective disintegration of large eddies and viscous-convective interactions among small eddies—I. General development and batch systems,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 42, no. 11, pp. 2597–2610, 1987. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(87)87011-2
- [56] J. Bałdyga, “Simplification of micromixing calculations: II. New applications,” *The Chemical Engineering Journal*, 1989. DOI: 10.1016/0300-9467(89)85003-8
- [57] J. Bałdyga, J. R. Bourne, and R. V. Gholap, “The influence of viscosity on mixing in jet reactors,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 50, no. 12, pp. 1877–1880, 1995. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(95)00049-B
- [58] G. Lipari and P. K. Stansby, “Review of experimental data on incompressible turbulent round jets,” *Flow, Turbulence and Combustion*, vol. 87, no. 1, pp. 79–114, 2011. DOI: 10.1007/s10494-011-9330-7
- [59] R. A. Antonia, B. R. Satyaprakash, and A. K. M. F. Hussain, “Measurements of dissipation rate and some other characteristics of turbulent plane and circular jets,” *The Physics of Fluids*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 695–700, 1980. DOI: 10.1063/1.863055
- [60] J. O. Hinze, *Turbulence* (McGraw-Hill series in mechanical engineering), 2d ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1975.
- [61] D. Liepmann, “Streamwise vorticity and entrainment in the near field of a round jet,” *Physics of Fluids A: Fluid Dynamics*, vol. 3, no. 5, pp. 1179–1185, 1991. DOI: 10.1063/1.858046
- [62] E. Tunestål, “Investigations of micromixing: In Alfa Laval’s ART® plate reactors,” Master Thesis, Chalmers University of Technology, 2012.
- [63] M. Maly, S. Schaper, R. Kuwertz, M. Hoffmann, J. Heck, and M. Schlüter, “Scale-up strategies of jet loop reactors for the intensification of mass transfer limited reactions,” *Processes*, vol. 10, no. 8, p. 1531, 2022. DOI: 10.3390/pr10081531

- [64] J. Bałdyga and J. R. Bourne, *Turbulent mixing and chemical reactions*. New York: Wiley, 1999.
- [65] J. Bałdyga and J. R. Bourne, “Interactions between mixing on various scales in stirred tank reactors,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 47, no. 8, pp. 1839–1848, 1992. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(92)80302-S
- [66] B. E. Launder and D. B. Spalding, “The numerical computation of turbulent flows,” *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 269–289, 1974. DOI: 10.1016/0045-7825(74)90029-2
- [67] H.-O. May, “Über die Berechnung des turbulenten runden Freistrahls unter Verwendung ähnlicher Lösungen,” *Forschung im Ingenieurwesen*, vol. 62, no. 10, pp. 271–280, 1996. DOI: 10.1007/BF02601937
- [68] M. Pipino and R. O. Fox, “Reactive mixing in a tubular jet reactor: A comparison of PDF simulations with experimental data,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 49, no. 24, pp. 5229–5241, 1994. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(94)00299-1
- [69] D. C. Wilcox, *Turbulence modeling for CFD*, 3rd ed. La Cãnada Calif.: DCW Industries, 2006.
- [70] N. T. Basse, “Turbulence Intensity and the Friction Factor for Smooth- and Rough-Wall Pipe Flow,” *Fluids*, vol. 2, no. 2, p. 30, 2017. DOI: 10.3390/fluids2020030
- [71] R. Pohorecki and J. Bałdyga, “New model of micromixing in chemical reactors: 1. General development and application to a tubular reactor,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Fundamentals*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 392–397, 1983. DOI: 10.1021/i100012a007
- [72] S. Corrsin, “The isotropic turbulent mixer: Part II. Arbitrary Schmidt number,” *AIChE Journal*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 870–877, 1964. DOI: 10.1002/aic.690100618
- [73] C. P. Fonte, D. F. Fletcher, P. Guichardon, and J. Aubin, “Simulation of micromixing in a T-mixer under laminar flow conditions,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 222, p. 115 706, 2020. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2020.115706
- [74] J. Bałdyga and J. R. Bourne, “A fluid mechanical approach to turbulent mixing and chemical reaction part III: Computational and experimental results for the new micromixing model,” *Chemical Engineering Communications*, vol. 28, no. 4-6, pp. 259–281, 1984. DOI: 10.1080/00986448408940137
- [75] J. Villermaux and L. Falk, “A generalized mixing model for initial contacting of reactive fluids,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 49, no. 24, pp. 5127–5140, 1994. DOI: 10.1016/0009-2509(94)00303-3
- [76] A. Kraus, S.-S. Ashrafmansouri, S. Osterroth, J. Krewin, and E. von Harbou, *Supplementary Material - Investigation of Micro- And Mesomixing in A Jet Loop Reactor*. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20663051
- [77] M. Assirelli, W. Bujalski, A. Eaglesham, and A. W. Nienow, “Study of micromixing in a stirred tank using a rushton turbine,” *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, vol. 80, no. 8, pp. 855–863, 2002. DOI: 10.1205/026387602321143390

- [78] M. Assirelli, W. Bujalski, A. Eaglesham, and A. W. Nienow, “Macro- and micromixing studies in an unbaffled vessel agitated by a Rushton turbine,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 63, no. 1, pp. 35–46, 2008. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2007.07.074
- [79] J. Fang and D. Lee, “Micromixing efficiency in static mixer,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 56, no. 12, pp. 3797–3802, 2001. DOI: 10.1016/S0009-2509(01)00098-7
- [80] L. Falk and J.-M. Commenge, “Performance comparison of micromixers,” *Chemical Engineering Science*, vol. 65, no. 1, pp. 405–411, 2010. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2009.05.045

Nomenclature

Latin letters

A	hydrogen ion	-
A	absorbance	-
A_1	model constant	-
A_2	model constant	m
A_3	model constant	-
A_4	model constant	m
A_5	model constant	-
B	dihydrogen borate ion	-
c	molar concentration	mol m^{-3}
C	iodate ion	-
C_μ	model constant	-
d	nozzle diameter	m
D	iodide ion	-
D_t	turbulent diffusivity	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
P^{diss}	energy dissipated in the reactor	$\text{kg m}^2 \text{s}^{-3}$
\dot{E}^{kin}	kinetic energy flux	$\text{kg m}^2 \text{s}^{-3}$
E	engulfment rate	s
I_t	turbulent intensity	-
k_1	reaction rate coefficient of Reaction (I)	$\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$
k_2	reaction rate coefficient of Reaction (II)	$\text{L}^{-4} \text{mol}^{-4} \text{s}$
k_t	turbulent kinetic energy	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$
K_{eq}	equilibrium constant of Reaction (III)	L mol^{-1}
m	mass	kg
P	iodine	-
Q	triiodide ion	-
R	boric acid	-
R	reaction source term	$\text{mol m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$
S_{II}	selectivity of Reaction (II) (A towards Q)	-
$S_{\text{II}}^{\text{ST}}$	selectivity of Reaction (II) for infinitely slow mixing	-
Sc_t	turbulent Schmidt number	-
t_{mix}	micromixing time	s
u	velocity	m s^{-1}
V	volume	m^3
\dot{V}	volumetric flow rate	$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
x	vertical distance to main nozzle	m
X	volume fraction	-

continued ...

... continued

X_S	segregation index	-
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Greek letters

α	Lagrangian lifetime	s
ε	energy dissipation rate	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-3}$
Λ_C	integral length scale of concentration fluctuations	m
ν	kinematic viscosity	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$
τ_D	time scale for turbulent dispersion	s
τ_S	time scale for inertial convective disintegration of large eddies	s

Subscripts

0	initial property
c	jet centerline property
<i>i</i>	species index
<i>k</i>	run variable engulfment model
end	at the end of reactions

Superscripts

(0)	relative to the volume of the whole fluid phase
(1)	relative to the volume of the reaction zone
(2)	relative to the volume of the bulk phase
(3)	relative to the volume of the mesomixed volume
start	start of experiments
end	end of experiments

Abbreviations

CFD	computational fluid dynamics
JLR	jet loop reactor
RMP	reaction mixing pump
VD	Villermaux-Dushman

S. Supplementary Information

S.1. Geometry of the JLR

Figure S.1.: Sketch of the JLR investigated in this study including the main dimensions. All measures are given in mm.

S.2. Components of the Experimental Setup

Table S.1.: Components of the experimental setup.

component	model	company	country
JLR	—	workshops of RPTU	Germany
jet nozzle	Mod.629 Bohrg.1.8 mm	Schlick	Germany
recycle pump	MCP-Z	Ismatech	Germany
filling pump	MCP-Z	Ismatech	Switzerland
HPLC pump	Smartline Pump 1000	KNAUER	Germany
flowmeter	RAGK	Rota Yokogawa	Germany
UV-vis	UVmini-1240	Shimadzu	Japan
spectrophotometry			
thermocouple	voltcraft K102	Conrad Electronic	Germany

S.3. Suppliers and Purity of Chemicals

Table S.2.: Suppliers and purity of the chemicals.

chemical	company	purity
sodium hydroxide (NaOH)	Merck	99.0-100.5 %
boric acid (H_3BO_3)	Carl Roth	≥ 99.5 %
potassium iodide (KI)	Thermo Fisher Scientific	99.0 %
potassium iodate (KIO_3)	Bernd Kraft	99.7 %
perchloric acid ($HClO_4$)	Th. Geyer	70.0 %

S.4. UV-vis Calibration Curve

Figure S.2.: Linear UV calibration curve of absorbance A as a function of the triiodide concentration c_Q .

S.5. Mixing Time Correlation

Figure S.3.: Theoretical relationship between the segregation index X_S and mixing time t_{mix} , derived using the engulfment micromixing model.

S.6. Mixing Experiments with VD Reaction System

Table S.3.: Experimental conditions for reactive mixing experiments using the Villermaux-Dushman reaction system, along with the resulting triiodide absorption measured via UV-vis spectroscopy. The buffer and acid solution concentrations remain consistent across all experiments.

Test No.	x / mm	$\dot{m}^{(2)}$ / g min ⁻¹	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ / mL min ⁻¹	$T^{\text{environment}}$ / °C	A / -
26082501	5	25	2.5	19.8	0.460
26082502	5	50	2.5	19.8	0.151
26082503	5	75	2.5	19.8	0.104
26082504	5	100	2.5	19.9	0.072
26082505	5	125	2.5	20.0	0.059
26082506	5	175	2.5	20.1	0.045
26082507	5	220	2.5	21.0	0.044
01092501	5	25	5.0	20.7	0.530
01092502	5	50	5.0	20.6	0.153
01092503	5	75	5.0	20.6	0.094
01092504	5	100	5.0	20.6	0.063
01092505	5	125	5.0	20.7	0.046
01092506	5	175	5.0	20.7	0.028
01092507	5	220	5.0	20.7	0.023
21082501	5	25	10.0	21.3	0.563
21082502	5	50	10.0	21.3	0.246
21082503	5	75	10.0	21.3	0.125

continued ...

... continued

Test No.	x /mm	$\dot{m}^{(2)}$ / g min ⁻¹	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ / mL min ⁻¹	$T^{\text{environment}}$ / °C	A / -
21082504	5	100	10.0	21.3	0.087
21082505	5	125	10.0	21.3	0.064
21082506	5	175	10.0	21.2	0.039
21082507	5	220	10.0	21.2	0.034
27082501	5	25	2.5	21.5	0.510
27082502	5	50	2.5	21.3	0.153
27082503	5	75	2.5	21.3	0.098
27082504	5	100	2.5	21.4	0.067
27082505	5	125	2.5	21.4	0.054
27082506	5	175	2.5	21.5	0.039
27082507	5	220	2.5	21.5	0.039
02092501	5	25	5.0	20.0	0.533
02092502	5	50	5.0	20.0	0.158
02092503	5	75	5.0	19.9	0.096
02092504	5	100	5.0	19.9	0.066
02092505	5	125	5.0	20.0	0.048
02092506	5	175	5.0	20.1	0.030
02092507	5	220	5.0	20.1	0.025
22082501	5	25	10.0	21.1	0.543
22082502	5	50	10.0	21.1	0.219
22082503	5	75	10.0	20.9	0.125
22082504	5	100	10.0	20.8	0.086
22082505	5	125	10.0	20.7	0.063
22082506	5	175	10.0	20.6	0.039
22082507	5	220	10.0	20.6	0.028
28082501	5	25	2.5	21.4	0.491
28082502	5	50	2.5	21.3	0.141
28082503	5	75	2.5	21.2	0.090
28082504	5	100	2.5	21.2	0.061
28082505	5	125	2.5	21.1	0.047
28082506	5	175	2.5	21.1	0.034
28082507	5	220	2.5	21.1	0.035
03092501	5	25	5.0	20.3	0.520
03092502	5	50	5.0	20.3	0.154
03092503	5	75	5.0	20.3	0.093
03092504	5	100	5.0	20.3	0.062
03092505	5	125	5.0	20.4	0.046
03092506	5	175	5.0	20.5	0.027
03092507	5	220	5.0	20.5	0.024
25082501	5	25	10.0	19.9	0.556
25082501	5	50	10.0	19.9	0.210
25082501	5	75	10.0	19.8	0.119
25082501	5	100	10.0	19.7	0.081
25082501	5	125	10.0	19.6	0.061

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Test No.	x /mm	$\dot{m}^{(2)}$ / g min ⁻¹	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ / mL min ⁻¹	$T^{\text{environment}}$ / °C	A / -
25082501	5	175	10.0	19.6	0.038
25082501	5	220	10.0	19.6	0.027
26062501	20	25	2.5	22.8	0.340
26062502	20	50	2.5	22.6	0.178
26062503	20	75	2.5	22.1	0.088
26062504	20	100	2.5	21.9	0.059
26062505	20	125	2.5	22.0	0.048
26062506	20	175	2.5	21.8	0.044
26062507	20	220	2.5	21.8	0.040
25062501	20	25	5.0	21.6	0.569
25062502	20	50	5.0	21.6	0.244
25062503	20	75	5.0	21.7	0.118
25062504	20	100	5.0	21.7	0.075
25062505	20	125	5.0	21.7	0.056
25062506	20	175	5.0	21.6	0.039
25062507	20	220	5.0	21.6	0.035
18062501	20	25	7.5	22.7	0.662
18062502	20	50	7.5	22.6	0.264
18062503	20	75	7.5	22.6	0.132
18062504	20	100	7.5	22.6	0.086
18062505	20	125	7.5	22.8	0.065
18062506	20	175	7.5	22.8	0.042
18062507	20	220	7.5	22.8	0.036
17062501	20	25	10.0	22.7	0.929
17062502	20	50	10.0	22.7	0.343
17062503	20	50	10.0	22.6	0.283
17062504	20	75	10.0	22.7	0.160
17062505	20	100	10.0	22.7	0.096
17062506	20	125	10.0	22.6	0.070
17062507	20	175	10.0	22.7	0.042
17062508	20	220	10.0	22.8	0.036
22072501	20	25	2.5	21.1	0.413
22072502	20	50	2.5	21.1	0.194
22072503	20	75	2.5	20.9	0.085
22072504	20	100	2.5	20.9	0.058
22072505	20	125	2.5	21.0	0.051
22072506	20	175	2.5	21.0	0.051
22072507	20	220	2.5	21.0	0.052
21072501	20	25	5.0	21.7	0.589
21072502	20	50	5.0	21.7	0.245
21072503	20	75	5.0	21.6	0.109
21072504	20	100	5.0	21.5	0.067
21072505	20	125	5.0	21.5	0.052
21072506	20	175	5.0	21.4	0.036

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Test No.	x /mm	$\dot{m}^{(2)}$ / g min ⁻¹	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ / mL min ⁻¹	$T^{\text{environment}}$ / °C	A / -
21072507	20	220	5.0	21.4	0.039
18072501	20	25	7.5	21.1	0.676
18072502	20	50	7.5	21.1	0.280
18072503	20	75	7.5	21.0	0.128
18072504	20	100	7.5	20.9	0.082
18072505	20	125	7.5	20.9	0.060
18072506	20	175	7.5	20.9	0.044
18072507	20	220	7.5	20.9	0.045
17072501	20	25	10.0	20.8	1.122
17072502	20	50	10.0	20.8	0.344
17072503	20	75	10.0	20.8	0.153
17072504	20	100	10.0	20.8	0.092
17072505	20	125	10.0	21.0	0.066
17072506	20	175	10.0	21.1	0.044
17072507	20	220	10.0	21.1	0.046
30072501	20	25	2.5	20.4	0.430
30072502	20	50	2.5	20.4	0.193
30072503	20	75	2.5	20.4	0.092
30072504	20	100	2.5	20.6	0.060
30072505	20	125	2.5	20.7	0.055
30072506	20	175	2.5	20.8	0.053
30072507	20	220	2.5	20.8	0.055
31072501	20	25	10.0	20.5	0.662
31072502	20	50	10.0	20.4	0.253
31072503	20	75	10.0	20.4	0.120
31072504	20	100	10.0	20.4	0.075
31072505	20	125	10.0	20.5	0.057
31072506	20	175	10.0	20.5	0.045
31072507	20	220	10.0	20.6	0.045
01082501	20	25	7.5	21.0	0.822
01082502	20	50	7.5	21.0	0.299
01082503	20	75	7.5	21.0	0.142
01082504	20	100	7.5	20.9	0.088
01082505	20	125	7.5	20.9	0.066
01082506	20	175	7.5	20.9	0.047
01082507	20	220	7.5	20.9	0.047
25072501	20	25	10.0	20.6	1.014
25072502	20	50	10.0	20.6	0.334
25072503	20	75	10.0	20.7	0.147
25072504	20	100	10.0	20.7	0.090
25072505	20	125	10.0	20.7	0.067
25072506	20	175	10.0	20.7	0.045
25072507	20	220	10.0	20.7	0.050
07082501	35	25	2.5	19.6	1.272

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Test No.	x /mm	$\dot{m}^{(2)}$ / g min ⁻¹	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ / mL min ⁻¹	$T^{\text{environment}}$ / °C	A / -
07082502	35	50	2.5	19.6	0.491
07082503	35	75	2.5	19.6	0.275
07082504	35	100	2.5	19.8	0.173
07082505	35	125	2.5	19.9	0.126
07082506	35	175	2.5	20.1	0.087
07082507	35	220	2.5	20.1	0.086
08082501	35	25	5.0	19.6	1.727
08082502	35	50	5.0	19.6	0.715
08082503	35	75	5.0	19.7	0.374
08082504	35	100	5.0	19.9	0.236
08082505	35	125	5.0	19.9	0.176
08082506	35	175	5.0	20.0	0.112
08082507	35	220	5.0	20.1	0.111
06082501	35	25	10.0	20.1	1.838
06082502	35	50	10.0	20.1	0.789
06082503	35	75	10.0	20.3	0.388
06082504	35	100	10.0	20.3	0.242
06082505	35	125	10.0	20.1	0.175
06082506	35	175	10.0	20.0	0.111
06082507	35	220	10.0	20.0	0.112
13082501	35	25	2.5	21.8	1.375
13082502	35	50	2.5	21.5	0.555
13082503	35	75	2.5	21.4	0.313
13082504	35	100	2.5	21.3	0.202
13082505	35	125	2.5	21.3	0.144
13082506	35	175	2.5	21.3	0.093
13082507	35	220	2.5	21.3	0.085
12082501	35	25	5.0	21.1	1.747
12082502	35	50	5.0	21.1	0.745
12082503	35	75	5.0	21.2	0.385
12082504	35	100	5.0	21.3	0.252
12082505	35	125	5.0	21.0	0.186
12082506	35	175	5.0	20.8	0.116
12082507	35	220	5.0	20.8	0.111
18082501	35	25	10.0	21.0	2.089
18082502	35	50	10.0	21.0	0.965
18082503	35	75	10.0	21.0	0.516
18082504	35	100	10.0	21.0	0.330
18082505	35	125	10.0	21.0	0.240
18082506	35	175	10.0	21.0	0.193
18082507	35	220	10.0	21.0	0.150
14082501	35	25	2.5	21.5	1.410
14082502	35	50	2.5	21.4	0.569
14082503	35	75	2.5	21.4	0.313

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Test No.	x /mm	$\dot{m}^{(2)}$ / g min ⁻¹	$\dot{V}^{(1)}$ / mL min ⁻¹	$T^{\text{environment}}$ / °C	A / -
14082504	35	100	2.5	21.4	0.201
14082505	35	125	2.5	21.4	0.148
14082506	35	175	2.5	21.4	0.091
14082507	35	220	2.5	21.4	0.087
15082501	35	25	5.0	21.6	1.838
15082502	35	50	5.0	21.6	0.738
15082503	35	75	5.0	21.5	0.383
15082504	35	100	5.0	21.5	0.250
15082505	35	125	5.0	21.5	0.183
15082506	35	175	5.0	21.5	0.112
15082507	35	220	5.0	21.5	0.114
19082501	35	25	10.0	21.2	2.101
19082502	35	50	10.0	21.4	1.016
19082503	35	75	10.0	21.5	0.569
19082504	35	100	10.0	21.4	0.348
19082505	35	125	10.0	21.3	0.239
19082506	35	175	10.0	21.3	0.179
19082507	35	220	10.0	21.3	0.140